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Deliverable 2.7

Initial report on the architecture used for the design, implementation, and integration scenarios of AAI, Monitoring Service, PID Service

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Abstract

This document outlines the current design that is being worked towards by the SUBMERSE consortium partners to realise the aims of the project. The system itself is composed of multiple parts. These include the sensing equipment, the storage and processing facilities, the dissemination facilities, the network which connects all the equipment together, the access control system, and the synchronisation of time and software across each of the sites. This initial report provides a detailed overview of the current implementation and integration scenarios for key operational tools in

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SUBMERSE, focusing on Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI), Monitoring Service, and Persistent Identifier (PID) Service.

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Executive Summary

This deliverable focuses on the work done by WP2 Task 5 that is responsible to offer operational tools such as Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI), Monitoring Service, and Persistent Identifier (PID) Service. The tasks strategy is to re-use existing services in order to reduce the overall cost of maintaining the operational tools and allow the infrastructure to become more sustainable. To achieve that we chose to use GÉANT's Core AAI platform (eduTEAMS) for AAI needs and the PID service from the European Persistent Identifier Consortium (ePIC). This initial report provides a detailed overview of the current implementation and integration scenarios for key operational tools in SUBMERSE, focusing on Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI), Monitoring Service, and Persistent Identifier (PID) Service. The architecture diagram provided (Figure 1) illustrates the envisaged flows and relationships among data producers (DAS, SOP, Polarimeter), site-specific services (Raw Storage, Filter Service, National Repository), and operational tools, highlighting how SUBMERSE orchestrates these components into a cohesive infrastructure. The information presented reflects a snapshot of the current design for the technical setup of the support services AAI, PIDS and Service Monitoring. As the project continues, the design will be refined. What is conveyed represents the thinking at the time of publication and is subject to change as the project progresses.

1 Introduction

The SUBMERSE project aims to develop a multinational and multi stakeholder research instrument, which can generate and sharing data about the earth using existing and in use submarine telecommunications cables. Such an instrument has not been developed before. The current work plan of SUBMERSE calls for at least 3 national sites to be deployed (in Portugal, Greece and Norway) and each site will host several services this poses significant challenges to how such a system could be set up reliably. It is also an opportunity to act as a pathfinder project to develop technologies which could benefit multiple research communities.

This document outlines the current design that is being worked towards by the SUBMERSE consortium partners to realise the aims of the project. The system itself is composed of multiple parts. These include the sensing equipment, the storage and processing facilities, the dissemination facilities, the network which connects all the equipment together, the access control system, and the synchronisation of time and software across each of the sites. This initial report provides a detailed overview of the current implementation and integration scenarios for key operational tools in SUBMERSE, focusing on Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI), Monitoring Service, and Persistent Identifier (PID) Service.

The architecture diagram below illustrates the envisaged flows and relationships among data producers (DAS, SOP, Polarimeter), site-specific services (Raw Storage, Filter Service, National Repository), and operational tools (AAI, Monitoring Service, Configuration Management DB), highlighting how SUBMERSE orchestrates these components into a cohesive infrastructure. SUBMERSE aims to re-use existing services where possible. To that extent we have selected to use GÉANT’s Core AAI platform (eduTEAMS) for AAI needs and the PID service from the European Persistent Identifier Consortium (ePIC). Such approach helps reduce the overall cost of maintaining the operational tools and allow the infrastructure to become more sustainable.

Figure 1.1 Operational Tools Architecture Diagram (C4 Model)

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2 Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure

2.1 Design

2.1.1 Objective

To manage access to services, the project will utilise the eduTEAMS Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI). The eduTEAMS service enables research communities to securely access and share common resources and services. Leveraging the ubiquitous presence of eduGAIN federated identities, eduTEAMS enables communities to securely authenticate and identify their users, organise them in groups, assign roles and centrally manage access rights for using community resources.

As research is not confined only in the research institutes and universities, eduTEAMS caters also for users coming from the industry or citizen scientists who may not have access to eduGAIN. This is achieved by supporting external (non-eduGAIN) identity providers, such as social networks providing federated identities, community identity providers and other platforms that can provide federated user identities. Communities can use the eduTEAMS service as the community AAI for their virtual collaborations.

To facilitate the onboarding of virtual collaborations, Work Package 2 Task 5 provides support for the configuration and integration of services from research infrastructures and public institutions which require access to the data and other services that will be developed by WP2 and WP3.

2.1.2 Components

eduTEAMS comprises four components:

- eduTEAMS Proxy & Identity Hub: The eduTEAMS Proxy is an SP-IdP Proxy with first-class support for the OpenID Connect (OIDC) ¹ and the Security Assertion Markup Language (SAML) ² protocols. It can connect SAML Identity Providers, OIDC Providers, SAML Service Providers (SPs), OIDC Relying Parties (RPs) enabling teams of researchers to use their preferred identity sources and services regardless of the authentication protocol used. The eduTEAMS Proxy is responsible for aggregating the user attributes from various identity sources, enforcing community and platform wide policies and providing one persistent user identifier and a harmonised set of attributes to the connected services.

¹ https://openid.net/specs/openid-connect-core-1_0.html

² <https://www.oasis-open.org/standard/saml/>

- eduTEAMS Discovery Service (DS): The eduTEAMS Discovery service provides a web interface for users to search and select their preferred identity provider.
- eduTEAMS Metadata Service (MDS): The eduTEAMS Metadata Service aggregates the metadata of all the SAML Identity and Service providers that are connected on the platform. It does so by aggregating the metadata feed of eduGAIN³, while allowing the platform administrators to also configure other local or remote metadata sources.
- eduTEAMS Membership Management Services (MMS): The eduTEAMS MMS provide the ability to users to create virtual organisations (VO), manage these VOs, invite users to collaborate, manage registration flows, organise user to groups and assign them roles and resource entitlements as needed within the collaborations.

2.1.3 Architecture

eduTEAMS follows a proxied model architecture that implements the AARC⁴ Blueprint Architecture (BPA). The AARC BPA defines a reference interoperability architecture that leverages established standards and best practices for identity and access management in research and collaboration environments. It addresses interoperability challenges by offering guidelines for federated access, facilitating seamless integration and collaboration among diverse infrastructures and services. This framework ensures adherence to security best practices and compliance with relevant standards. The eduTEAMS architecture, along with the components described in Section 2.1.2, are illustrated in Figure 2.1 below.

³ <https://edugain.org/>

⁴ Authentication and Authorisation for Research and Collaboration (AARC) <https://aarc-community.org/>

Figure 2.1 Representation of eduTEAMS architecture

2.2 Implementation

eduTEAMS is based on the GÉANT Core AAI Platform which integrates essential components and protocols to support advanced identity and access management services tailored for research and collaboration environments. Key technologies include:

Authentication and Authorisation Protocols:

- SAML: Used for federated authentication and single sign-on (SSO).
- OIDC: Provides authentication and authorisation capabilities using OAuth 2.0, suitable for modern web applications and APIs.

Proxy and Identity Hub:

- Responsible for integrating with both SAML Identity Providers (IdPs) and OIDC Providers (OPs), as well as serving as a Service Provider (SP) and Relying Party (RP) for these protocols.
- Aggregates user attributes from multiple identity sources and enforces policies across connected services.

Discovery Service:

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- Provides a web interface where users can discover and select their preferred identity provider (IdP) for authentication.
- Facilitates the redirection of users to the selected IdP for authentication and authorization.

Metadata Service:

- Aggregates metadata from all connected SAML IdPs and SPs, including metadata feeds from eduGAIN and other configured sources.
- Ensures consistent and up-to-date metadata for federated authentication across the platform.

Membership Management Service:

- Enables users to create and manage virtual organisations (VOs), invite collaborators, manage group memberships, and assign roles and permissions within these collaborations.
- Organises users into groups and manages resource entitlements as required by collaboration needs. Provide support for an Attribute Authority (AA) capability.

Integration Capabilities:

- Provides APIs and integration points for connecting external services to leverage eduTEAMS for authentication and authorisation based on either SAML or OIDC.

Monitoring and Logging:

- Includes monitoring tools and logging mechanisms to track authentication events, service usage metrics, and operational performance.
- Facilitates troubleshooting and auditing of access activities within the platform.

2.3 Integration

Service owners can connect their services to eduTEAMS using either OIDC or SAML. As illustrated in Figure 2.2 AAI Integration Process, service registration requests are submitted via the eduTEAMS registration form⁵ and reviewed by the eduTEAMS Support team. Required details include service and contact information, legal entity name, and compliance with policies like the GÉANT Data Protection Code of Conduct⁶ and the Sirtfi security framework⁷. SAML2 services (SAML Service Providers - SPs) need to provide eduGAIN publication status and metadata URL, while OIDC services (OIDC Relying Parties - RPs) specify OAuth 2.0 grants and redirect URLs. After submission, owners receive a confirmation, and the request is reviewed with notifications sent by email.

Figure 2.2 AAI Integration Process

⁵ https://webapp.eduteams.org/sp_request

⁶ https://www.geant.org/uri/Documents/GEANT_DP_CoC_ver1.0.pdf

⁷ <https://refeds.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/01/Sirtfi-1.0.pdf>

Post-approval, the service owner needs to configure their service based on the chosen protocol, whether OIDC or SAML. The eduTEAMS documentation⁸ includes configuration examples for commonly used OIDC and SAML client libraries:

SAML Integration:

- Example of SAML metadata for SAML SPs⁹
- Connecting a Shibboleth SP to eduTEAMS OIDC

Integration:

- OIDC Client Configuration Options¹⁰
- Connecting a Keycloak RP to eduTEAMS
- Using Client Credentials grant at eduTEAMS

Once the service is configured, user attributes, such as the Community User Identifier, Display Name, and Email, are accessible as OIDC claims or SAML attributes. Details on mandatory and optional attributes are available in the Attributes available to Relying Parties guide¹¹.

⁸ <https://wiki.geant.org/display/eduTEAMS/Documentation>

⁹ <https://wiki.geant.org/display/eduTEAMS/Example+of+SAML+metadata+for+services>

¹⁰ <https://wiki.geant.org/display/eduTEAMS/OIDC+Client+Configuration+Options>

¹¹ <https://wiki.geant.org/display/eduTEAMS/Attributes+available+to+Relying+Parties>

3 Service Monitoring

3.1 Design

3.1.1 Objective

The current work plan of SUBMERSE calls for at least 3 national sites to be deployed (in Portugal, Greece and Norway) and each site will host several services that must run reliably to ensure the workflow remains/is operational.

The Service Monitoring Activity is responsible to monitor the Reliability and Availability and the status of the services of this infrastructure and to alert the service operators if any issue occurs. Monitoring is the key service needed to gain insights into an infrastructure. It needs to be continuous and on-demand to quickly detect, correlate, and analyse data for a fast reaction to anomalous behaviour. The challenge of this type of monitoring is how to quickly identify and correlate problems before they affect end-users and ultimately the productivity of the organisation. The key functionalities that are required to be offered by the Monitoring service are:

- Reporting availability and reliability,
- Visualisation of the services status,
- Provide dashboard interfaces that can be targeted towards both Providers and End Users (e.g. Researchers),
- Sending real-time alerts to Providers (Service operators).

3.1.2 Components

The main components of the Monitoring service are depicted in the high-level architecture diagram and described in paragraph 3.1.3 Architecture.

Monitoring Engine(s): this component executes the service checks against the distributed infrastructure and delivers the metric data (probe check results) to the Messaging Service.

Sources of Truth: The Monitoring system supports a number of connector plugins that are able to fetch topology, metrics and factors from various sources such as the CMDB and the Resource Catalogue. A Metric and Profile Management Component allows checks (probes) to be defined and associated with specific Services. Each combination of checks and service types forms a profile.

Messaging: The monitoring system uses a Pub/Sub Messaging Service to connect its components.

Computations & Analytics: Computational jobs are defined for ingesting data, calculating status and availability/reliability and a management service automatically configures, deploys and executes those jobs on a

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distributed processing engine for stateful computations. This component analyses the monitoring results and sends notifications based on a set of rules, to inform the Service Providers about the status of their services.

WEB API: RESTful HTTP API service that provides access to status and availability/reliability results. It supports token-based authentication and authorisation with established roles. Results are provided in JSON Format.

WEB UI: The Web UI is the component to present the information about the status of the services. The global information from the primary and heterogeneous data sources is retrieved by means of the different plugins. The collected information is structured and organised within configuration files in the service and, finally, made available to the web application without the need for any further computations. This modular architecture is conceived to make it easy to add new data sources and to use cached information if a primary source is unavailable. The resulting data is exposed through a RESTful web service interface.

The following Table 3.1: Service Monitoring Definitions defines key terms that explain how the Monitoring service works and the types of information a Provider should supply/define to start to use the service.

Definitions

Term	Definition
Tenant	The tenant is an isolated instance of the Monitoring service that relies on common components and provides the user with its own environment.
Topology	Monitoring service requires the following topology information to monitor services: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the services and service endpoints they are running • the way they are organised (e.g. groups of sites, groups of services), • the service actors (owners, admins, contact points). • The topology can be further extended with attributes needed for individual probes (e.g. service port or URL, path to be used in case of storage services, e.g.).
Metric	A metric is a small piece of software that checks specific functionality of a given service. For example, a metric such as Portal-WebCheck runs on a site and checks if the HTTP connection responds correctly or not.
Probe	A probe is a small piece of software that implements single or multiple tests. The probe must comply with the guidelines for monitoring probes.
Registry of Probes and metrics	Monitoring Service provides a registry of probes ¹² and metrics. New probes and metrics can be added to the registry with the support of the Monitoring team.
Metric Profile	A Metric Profile ¹³ is used to associate a Service with the corresponding metrics.

¹² <https://argo.eu.github.io/argo-monitoring/docs/Monitoring/guidelines>

¹³ <https://argo.eu.github.io/argo-monitoring/docs/Profiles/aggregation-profile/>

Aggregation Profile	An Aggregation Profile defines how to aggregate service statuses into higher hierarchical grouping (i.e. a service_group) status results. They are used to define logical rules on how to aggregate individual service status computations into groups.
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Table 3.1 Service Monitoring Definitions

3.1.3 Architecture

The Figure 3.1 below explains the Service Monitoring Architecture. Monitoring service collects status (metrics) results from one or more monitoring engine(s) deployed across distributed infrastructure and delivers daily and/or monthly availability (A) and reliability (R) results for monitored services. Status results and A/R metrics are presented through a Web UI, with the ability for a user to drill-down from the availability of a site to individual test results that contributed to the computed figure.

Figure 3.1 Service Monitoring Architecture

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3.2 Implementation

The proposed solution is based on ARGO monitoring and will monitor a wide range of services and provide operational insights for different built-in key performance indicators. A modular, pluggable architecture will be used so that the service can easily support a wide range of integrations as needed. The complexity of a system presents a big impact on monitoring.

ARGO Monitoring provides an easy path to gain powerful insights. The ARGO Monitoring service starts monitoring the service by checking its liveness /health of the service. The main focus is to check the availability and reliability of the services, as well as groups of services by simulating the actions that the respective user would do interacting with it. For instance, in the case of a file transfer server (FTP), the service tries to transfer, save and delete a file in the server. These tests are performed at regular random intervals (e.g. every hour or 15 minutes) and their results are recorded to be included in the measuring of the availability and reliability of the service. The service supports different profiles for creating the topology and grouping of services and the algorithm for calculating the availability and reliability of services. The calculations are performed in big data management and processing infrastructures (use of Apache Flink platform) which provide results both in real time and their correction at regular intervals. The service publishes the results of its calculations in real time, thus allowing the creation of a control panel of the status of the services (through a special interface that has been created) and provides the possibility of timely notification (alerts via email as well as SMS and slack messages) of administrators in case to detect an error. Argo monitoring provides a modern and comprehensive web-ui in which users can easily view details and results (status results and a/r scores) on items monitored. Users can navigate through the different layers of topology (groups, services, endpoints) and with various levels of granularity (monthly, daily, etc...)

Figure 3.2 Screenshot of the ui of Service Monitoring

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3.3 Implementation

3.3.1 Add a service to be monitored

The following 3.3 demonstrates the steps for each service provider to enable monitoring of their Service. Each service provider needs to collaborate with the Monitoring team to choose or develop the necessary metrics needed for each service to be monitored.

Figure 3.3 Service Monitoring Workflow to Monitor a Service

The monitoring services allows the customer can access the following information via an API:

- A/R information about the service and its service components
- Status information about the service and its service components
- The topology and grouping of the service

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4 Persistent Identifiers Service

4.1 Design

4.1.1 Objective

The current work plan of SUBMERSE calls that the data that will be produced by each site is expected to be in the order of 7TB per day and they will need to be stored for the foreseeable future according to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles¹⁴. To meet the ambitions of the project and to ensure F.A.I.R. use of the data produced persistent identifiers (PID) will be used to manage the persistence and provenance of the data. A PID acts as pointers to an output. It identifies and locates an entity regardless of where it is hosted or published and enables its unambiguous and long-term identification. The main goal is to use PIDs to ensure that data are findable for the foreseeable future. The granularity of PID assignment is defined according to the Data Management Plan and the requirements of Work Package 3.

A PID is a unique identifier (label) assigned to a resource, digital object or entity, designed to facilitate long-term referencing and accessibility. Unlike regular identifiers, which may change or become obsolete, PIDs are intended to provide long-term stability and reliability for referencing and accessing digital resources. PIDs are commonly used in scholarly communication, research data management, digital archives, and other domains, where reliable identification and linking of digital objects are essential. The primary characteristics of PID include uniqueness, persistence, resolvability (the ability to be resolved to a location or metadata), and interoperability (compatibility across different systems and platforms). Overall, PIDs play a critical role in enhancing the discoverability, accessibility, and long-term preservation of digital information in various domains. PIDs are crucial components of the digital information ecosystem, providing a means to uniquely identify and reference digital objects such as publications, datasets, software, and other research outputs.

4.1.2 Components

The PID Service is based on components that are responsible for the management of the PIDs. The components of service that are includes:

- **The Service:** The core component that stores and resolves handles. It ensures that each handle is globally unique and can be reliably resolved to the current location or metadata of the associated digital object.

¹⁴ For more information See D1.2 Data management plan and <https://force11.org/info/the-fair-data-principles/>

- **The Management Library:** A library that provides an interface for users to interact with the service. The library allows users to create, update, and resolve handles programmatically. The library also ensures secure access to handle management functionalities (user authentication mechanism).
- **Metadata Management:** A Component that allows the association of metadata with handles. This includes the process for defining, storing, and updating metadata linked to each handle.
- **Reverse lookup Component:** This component involves finding the digital objects or metadata associated with a given PID. It typically refers to querying the metadata stored with the handle to retrieve relevant information about the digital object it identifies.

GRNET As part of the ePIC consortium is offering PID services with the following functionalities also available:

- **Replication and Redundancy:** Mechanisms to ensure the high availability and reliability of the handle service. This typically involves replication of handle data across multiple nodes and geographical locations.
- **Monitoring and Logging:** Tools and services that provide monitoring of the service's health, performance, and usage.

By incorporating these components, PID Service ensures a robust and reliable system for managing persistent identifiers, which is essential for maintaining the integrity and accessibility of digital resources over time.

4.1.3 Architecture

GRNET offers the PID service in cooperation with the European Persistent Identifier Consortium (ePIC). ePIC provides PID services for the European and wider international research community under the top-level Handle prefix "21dot". The goal of ePIC is to set up and maintain a reliable joint service for registering, storing and resolving persistent identifiers based on handles for the research community. ePIC is set up as a highly reliable, persistent and high-performance service. This is achieved through a network of strong data centres in Europe (including GRNET) that share the same service, the same API and that have implemented a redundancy scheme. When one centre is out of order the other centres will still resolve the PIDs.

4.2 Architecture

The proposed solution is based on ePIC. Handle Prefixes and are globally resolvable via the Handle.net Global Resolving Network. Managing PIDs involves several key tasks and considerations to ensure their effective use and long-term sustainability. Assigning unique PIDs to digital objects is the first step in managing persistent identifiers. This process involves registering the PID and associating it with the correct metadata describing the identified resource. Managing metadata associated with PIDs is essential for enhancing the discoverability, accessibility, and usability of digital objects. This includes creating and maintaining descriptive metadata describing the identified resources, updating metadata as needed to reflect changes or updates to the resources, and ensuring metadata quality and consistency across the PID ecosystem.

Managing the lifecycle of persistent identifiers based on the Data Management Plan involves also updating or deactivating identifiers as needed and ensuring compliance with relevant policies and standards. Considerations

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include implementing policies for identifier versioning, archival preservation, and retirement. This includes data in various states of movement and storage like dataflow, buffer storage, storage and repository data.

Managing a PID consists of minting, resolving and updating the persistent identifiers. With regards to minting, this registration process involves, as already mentioned, providing metadata about the identified resource, such as title, creation date, access rights and more, to facilitate discovery and retrieval by users and systems. GRNET PID Service provides, for us, a suitable HTTP API to mint PIDs.

To resolve the PID, the ePIC resolution mechanism allows users and systems to resolve PIDs to the associated resource or metadata. Actionable PIDs are also supported to facilitate access to the identified resources. Again, the GRNET PID Service provides a HTTP API to resolve and update the PID either directly to the metadata page, or the resource. The GRNET service also allows part of a PID to be updated, allowing greater flexibility and scalability in deployment.

4.3 Integration

Integrating Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) into a service involves several steps and considerations to ensure seamless, reliable, and efficient management of digital objects. Below are the key fundamentals and the actions available involved in integrating PIDs into a service.

4.3.1 The Fundamentals of PIDs

Name	Description
Prefix	Designates administrative domain, created by an issuing instance. The Prefixes will be issued by EPIC / DONA. GRNET host the Prefixes for SUBMERSE.
Suffix	A Name used for your Resource under the Prefix.
User	The technology used and the name we use for PIDs in EPIC.
Handle	User with permissions to manage PIDs under a Prefix. Each user may have different permissions.
Handle values	Values that describe PID with types. Default handle value types is as follows: HS_ADMIN, HS_VLIST, HS_SECKEY, HS_PUBKEY, HS_SITE, HS_SERV, HS_ALIAS, EMAIL, URL, URN, INET_HOST, 10320/LOC.
Handle record	The way the PID is saved in the handle system (database)

Table 4.1 PID Definitions

In the following image the fundamentals and the connections between them are displayed.

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Figure 4.1 PID Fundamentals

4.3.2 Suffix Generation

Every identifier consists of two parts: its prefix and a unique local name under the prefix known as its suffix Copy
< PREFIX > / < SUFFIX > (e.g. 21.T15999/123456745).

Any suffix - local name must be unique under its local namespace. The uniqueness of a prefix and a local name under that prefix ensures that any identifier is globally unique within the context of the System. It's up to the user to decide the names of the PIDs. You may use

- a number
- a string
- a UUID
- a pattern based on the community context

In all examples in this manual we use a UUID generator.

4.3.3 Create, mint a PID

The example that we describe below is to create a PID for a resource with url=https://www.submerse.eu/. This is the simplest example on how to mint a PID. Apart from HTTP POST, HTTP PUT can be used for both resource creation and resource updates. If the user wants to be sure that a new PID will be created the user must first check if it exists. If the user doesn't check the existence of a PID based on the suffix, it is possible that he will update the data of an existing one.

Example

```
curl -H "Content-Type:application/json" -u "301%3AUSERNAME:KEY" -X POST --data
<<DATA>> ENDPOINT/YOUR-PID-NAME
```

With **data**

```
{
  "values": [
    {
      "index": 1,
      "type": "URL",
      "data": {
        "format": "string",
        "value": "https://www.submerse.eu"
      }
    },
    {
      "index": 2,
      "type": "title",
      "data": {
        "format": "string",
        "value": "A test pid"
      }
    },
    {
      "index": 101,
      "type": "HS_ADMIN",
      "data": {
        "format": "admin",
        "value": {
          "handle": "{{USERNAME}}",
          "index": 301,
          "permissions": "011111110011"
        }
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

The Response that the user will get is

```
{
  "responseCode": 1,
  "handle": "PREFIX/YOUR-PID-NAME"
}
```

4.3.4 Update PID

The user wants to update the values of an existing PID. This action is similar to the Create action. The basic parameters are the same as in CREATE a PID.

Example: If the user wants to update only the Url of the PID

```
curl -H "Content-Type:application/json" -u "301%3AUSERNAME:KEY" -X PUT --data
<<DATA>> ENDPOINT/YOUR-PID-NAME?index=1
```

Deliverable D2.7

Initial report on the architecture used for the design, implementation, and integration scenarios of AAI, Monitoring Service, PID Service

Document ID: Operational Tools, Report

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With data

```
{
  "values": [
    {
      "index": 1,
      "type": "URL",
      "data": {
        "format": "string",
        "value": "https://submerse.eu/news/"
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

Example If the user wants to update all the values of the PID

```
curl -H "Content-Type:application/json" -u "301%3AUSERNAME:KEY" -X PUT --data
<<DATA>> ENDPOINT/YOUR-PID-NAME?index=various
```

With data

```
{
  "values": [
    {
      "index": 1,
      "type": "URL",
      "data": {
        "format": "string",
        "value": "https://submerse.eu/news/"
      }
    },
    {
      "index": 2,
      "type": "title",
      "data": {
        "format": "string",
        "value": "the new test"
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

In both cases The Response that the user will get is

```
{
  "responseCode": 1,
  "handle": "PREFIX/YOUR-PID-NAME"
}
```

5 Deployment Timeline

The deployment of the operational tools (AAI, Monitoring Service, PID Service) will be executed in phased stages aligned with the overall SUBMERSE project milestones. The following timeline outlines key activities across participating national sites (Portugal, Greece, Norway) and centrally hosted services, ensuring readiness for data collection, monitoring, and access provisioning.

Phase	Milestone	Target Date	Status
Phase 1: Preparation	Requirements consolidation, component selection, and planning	May 2023 – Jul 2023	Completed
Phase 2: AAI Deployment	eduTEAMS integration with first services (SAML/OIDC test cases)	Sep 2023 – Oct 2023	Completed
Phase 3: Monitoring Setup	ARGO-based Monitoring deployment and test with dummy services	Sep 2023 – Dec 2023	Completed
Phase 4: PID Setup	PID Minting system deployment	2023 – Oct 2024	Completed
Phase 5: Site-Level Testing	Pilot deployment at national sites with simulated data flows	Oct 2024 – Nov 2024	Delayed
Phase 6: Full Integration	Integration of AAI, Monitoring and PID services with real workflows	Mar 2025– Nov 2025	Pending
Phase 7: Continuous Operation	Service monitoring, SLA enforcement, incremental improvements	Nov 2025 onwards	Pending

Each phase includes feedback loops with intern¹⁵al reviews, configuration refinement, and stakeholder training as necessary. The goal is to ensure operational resilience and scalability ahead of full-scale data ingestion expected in Q3 2025.

¹⁵ As the timeline was added on the revised version of this deliverable , It indicates the current status at the time of resubmission of this deliverable in July 2025.

6 Conclusions

This report is about the work performed so far by WP2 Task 5 and highlights the key aspects such as reliability and sustainability of the implementation and integration of SUBMERSE's operational tools. The tasks strategy is to re-use existing services in order to reduce the overall cost of maintaining the operational tools and allow the infrastructure to become more sustainable. To achieve that we chose to use GÉANT's Core AAI platform (eduTEAMS) for AAI needs and the PID service from the European Persistent Identifier Consortium (ePIC). This initial report provides a detailed overview of the current implementation and integration scenarios for key operational tools in SUBMERSE, focusing on Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI), Monitoring Service, and Persistent Identifier (PID) Service. While there are areas that need improvement, particularly in terms of integration and user experience, the overall infrastructure is robust and capable of supporting the infrastructure's growth and operational needs. For a deeper dive into each tool's implementation details and specific integration scenarios, please refer to the detailed sections within the full report. The focus of the task in the next period is devise the necessary access model/framework to be able to disseminate the data collected by the three national sites securely.

7 Glossary

Acronym	Definition
AARC	Authentication and Authorisation for Research and Collaboration
DAS	Distributed Acoustic Sensing
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DONA	DONA Foundation (dona.net)
EIDA	European Integrated Data Archive
EMSO	European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EPOS	The European Plate Observing System
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
FDSN	International Federation of Digital Seismograph Networks
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
NREN	National Research and Education Network
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OTDR	Optical Time-Domain Reflectometer
PID	Persistent Identifier
RCN	Research Coordination Network
REST-API	Restful Application Programming Interface
SOP	State of Polarisation
SUBMERSE	SUBMarine cablEs for ReSearch and Exploration
XML	Extensible Markup Language